

Effect of Defect on the Behaviour of Composites

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ABSTRACT

An experimental investigation was conducted to study the effect of defect on impact-damaged cfrp specimens. Several laminates of different ply orientations and ply thicknesses (1-2.7mm) were impact-damaged by simulated dropped tools and then tension-compression ($R=-1$) or tension-tension ($R=0.1$) loaded. Results suggest a practicable damage tolerance with nearly invisible defects.

INTRODUCTION

The application of cfrp laminates to aircraft structures has demonstrated the capability to save weight and improve aircraft performance. This advantage can be diminished by impact loads. Low-velocity impact may occur during manufacture, maintenance or in service caused by hailstones, runway debris or accidentally dropped tools. These impacts can cause significant internal damages which result in reduction of load-carrying capability and reliability of the structure. The purpose of an ongoing program in our institute is to determine first the damage characteristics resulting from the localized low-energy impact loading of cfrp composite plates, and second the behaviour of the damaged specimens under harmonic fatigue loading. Strength, stiffness, and damage propagation were measured to get an idea of the effect of nearly invisible damages under harmonic fatigue loading on lifetime and reliability.

MATERIALS AND TEST METHODS

Laminate built-up. Two prepreg materials, T300/Code69 from Fothergill and Harvey and T300/914C from Ciba Geigy, were laminated in 7 different lay-ups (Table I) as plane plates. The plates (300x300mm) were cured in an autoclave according to the manufacturers recommended cure cycles. Laminates 1 to 4 had a protective E-glass fabric ply style 120 (0.1 mm thick) on both sides of the plates, applied dry and soaked by surplus resin during molding /1/. Laminates 1 and 3 were extensively examined in West Germany /2/. Variations thereof (laminates 2 and 4) were accomplished for reducing edge delamination under tension fatigue loading. Laminates 6 and 7 were specifically fabricated to study the influence of the stacking sequence on damage and damage propagation.

lam.	prepreg	fibre cont.	stacking sequence	surface sheet	thickness
1	T300/Code69	56 vol. %	(0 ₂ /±45/0 ₂ /±45/90)sym	E-glass style 120	2.7 mm
2	T300/Code69	68 vol. %	(0 ₂ /±45/90/±45/0 ₂)sym	E-glass style 120	2.3 mm
3	T300/914C	55 vol. %	(0 ₂ /±45/0 ₂ /±45/90)sym	E-glass style 120	2.7 mm
4	T300/914C	55 vol. %	(0 ₂ /±45/90/±45/0 ₂)sym	E-glass style 120	2.7 mm
5	T300/914C	54 vol. %	(0/90/0/±45/0)sym	-	1.8 mm
6	T300/Code69	55 vol. %	(0/90/±45)sym	-	1.0 mm
7	T300/Code69	55 vol. %	(0/±45/90)sym	-	1.0 mm

Table I Laminate construction

Impact Damage Procedure. Drop weight tests were performed employing steel impactors with variable weight and exchangeable tip to simulate typical tools dropped from various heights (see Fig.1). The specimen plates were circularly clamped. An accelerometer on top of the impactor enabled the determination of force, displacement, and energy consumption. Impact conditions are listed in Table II.

Fig.1-Drop weight apparatus

Fig.2-Instrumented impact test

lam.	mass	drop height	abs. energy	int. delam.	vis. damage	tip
1	0.244 kg	1.93 m	2.8 J ± 23%	440 mm ² ± 20%	30 mm	10mmØ, ball
2	0.255 kg	1.93 m	2.7 J ± 7%	365 mm ² ± 15%	90 mm	10mmØ, ball
3	0.244 kg	1.93 m	2.0 J ± 13%	270 mm ² ± 30%	30 mm	10mmØ, ball
4	0.244 kg	1.93 m	2.0 J ± 7%	308 mm ² ± 20%	20 mm	10mmØ, ball
5	0.306 kg	1.00 m	1.6 J ± 9%	212 mm ² ± 19%	only cracks	10mmØ, ball
6	0.298 kg	0.25 m	0.18J ± 48%	123 mm ² ± 62%	no	5mmØ, blunt
7	0.298 kg	0.25 m	0.15J ± 23%	205 mm ² ± 19%	no	5mmØ, blunt

Table II Damage characteristics

Laminates 1 to 4 were impact-damaged according to the test scheme in Fig.2. In this experimental device the energy conversion was additionally obtained by measurement of the oscillation of the plate clamping equipment suspended from the ceiling as a pendulum. Additionally, plate deformation was documented (Moire-fringes) by flash photography. An example of an impact test evaluation is given in Fig.3. Environmental conditions were not controlled except with plates of laminate 2, which were kept dry by sealing them into plastic bags immediately after production until just before impacting. Room temperature was about 23 C.

Fig.3-Impact test evaluation (example).

Post-Impact Tests. To determine the effect of impact damages on cfrp specimens post-impact static and fatigue tests were performed. Coupons (250x50mm and 120x40mm) were cut off for axial static and cyclic tension-tension and tension-compression loading ($R=0.1$ resp. $R=-1$). Tension-compression loading condition is one of the most severe for the investigated laminates /3/. An antibuckling device was developed for least impediment of damage propagation supporting only the edges. On the coupons 30x70mm were kept clear /4/. US-C-scan, temperature, and electro-optical strain measurements were used to monitor damage propagation. The stiffness decrease (tension-compression) was related in all cases to a base distance of $l=50\text{mm}$ in the middle of which the defects were located. The environmental conditions during all tests were about 23 C room temperature and 30% - 40% relative humidity.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Impact Damages. Parameters of damage introduction were chosen with the aim of generating defects which are hardly to detect or invisible to the naked eye at front of impact-loaded laminates. Usually, the introduced defects were intraply cracks, interlaminar delamination, and some fibre breakages near impact locus on and beneath the back surface relative to impact /1,5/. The damage started at less than 800N contact force and did not exceed 1700N for laminate 4. Fig.4 presents a selection of damages if energy and contacting tip shape are varied /8/. With increasing momentum of the impactor the absorbed energy increases, too, until penetration. On the other hand the internal delamination area reaches a maximum and then drops again to a limit which is determined by impactor shape: the smaller the face, the smaller the damaged area /5/. Damage sizes determined by US-C-scan

Fig.4-Damaged faces and internal delamination extension of laminate 2, impacted with varied energies (left, tip:ball 10mm \varnothing) and varied impactor shape (right, mass $m=0.26\text{kg}$). Contact velocity $v=6.15\text{m/s}$; clamp diam. $D=160\text{mm}$.

Fig.5-Fatigue test results

Fig.6-Fatigue test results

Fig.7-Fatigue test results

and absorbed energies are summarized in Table II. Laminates 1 & 2 containing Code 69 resin absorb significantly more energy and exhibit larger internal delamination zones than laminates 3 & 4 containing 914C resin. This difference could be attributed to the curing stresses in both resin systems. The intralaminar stress transverse to fibre direction, following the classical laminate theory, is 55N/mm^2 in laminates 1 & 2, resp. 31N/mm^2 in laminates 3 & 4 at room temperature in dry laminates. The variation of stacking sequence shows no significant effect on absorbed energy.

Fatigue Test Results. Figs. 5, 6 and 7 present the fatigue test data of damaged and sound specimens of laminates 1 to 7. The data prove the lower damage sensitivity of 914C compared to Code69. Damaged specimens of 914C as well as sound ones have a higher fatigue strength than the Code69 ones. Comparison of stacking sequence variation (laminates 1, 3 to 2, 4) yields no cognition. The small enhancement in fatigue strength of laminate 4 with damages to that of laminate 1 is not considered to be significant. Laminate 5 owing different impact damage shows

no fundamental distinction to laminates 3 and 4. Only the decline of fatigue strength is shifted towards higher number of load cycles with sound and damaged specimens. The development of delaminated area in laminates 6 & 7 under tension-tension-fatigue is small /9/. Although the interlaminar normal stress at the free edges have different signs for both laminates the free edge delamination increases faster than the impact induced delamination. The scant residual strength data do not allow profound interpretation except to note that residual strength mostly exceed the fatigue curve, often reach the static strength values and sometimes go beyond it, as published elsewhere with sound laminates /4,5/. It seems that the behaviour of damaged and sound specimens match better with the sudden death model than with the degradation model /2/. However, looking at damage propagation in damaged specimens, there was an apparent sudden death only with laminates 1 & 5. In these laminates no damage propagation could be noticed visually or by C-scan until abrupt breakdown. With laminates 3, 4, 6 and 7 damage propagation at higher stress levels but could be observed. But

Fig.8-Stiffness degradation during fatigue loading (R = -1)

Fig.9-Stiffness degradation during fatigue loading (bending)

Fig.10-Synchronism of temperature rise, stiffness degradation and delamination growth during fatigue testing

CONCLUSIONS

Cfrp composites are susceptible to hit and stroke. Especially composites with only one or two fibre orientations exhibit few but long cracks parallel to fibre direction at low-velocity and low-energy impact. Composites should be composed of many thin layers with alternating orientation. This turns arising intraply cracks to interply delamination thus limiting the damage extent. Stacking sequence has not a remarkable influence on impact damage of the investigated laminates. Furtheron, curing induced built-up stresses facilitate damage extension and should be minimized. Nearly invisible impact damages do not considerably diminish the tension capacities but reduce the compression strength as the test data may suggest. But this can be a deception. The ratio damage size to sample size -prescribed by the available test apparatus- is unrealistic considering the size of a wing panel. As a very rough thumb rule the compression strength is reduced by the ratio damaged cross section to total cross section. This is true with high static and dynamic stress levels for all investigated laminates. However the strength diminishes at low stress levels. Since a structure is usually designed for long life the impairment of strength at least in laminates 1 to 4 by introduced damages must be low in a real structure as long as buckling does not become a problem. Observable defect extension is not a reliable indicator of degradation on the whole, as shown by laminate 5. Further research is necessary and is foreseen taking into account more realistic conditions, e.g. dynamic loads preceding impact, stresses at impact, and random fatigue loads following the impact.

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